

LINGUOCULTUROLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE LEXICON REPRESENTING COLOR-TONE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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Abstract. This article provides information on the linguoculturological features of color-tone lexicon in English and Uzbek, the place of lexicography in Uzbek and English, active lexical units in languages and what their lexical-semantic features consist of.

Keywords: lexicon, lexicography, lexical units, phraseology, phraseological units, terms, dictionaries.

ЛИНГВОКУЛЬТУРОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ЛЕКСИКИ, ПРЕДСТАВЛЯЮЩЕЙ ЦВЕТОВОЙ ТОН В АНГЛИЙСКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ

Аннотация. В этой статье представлена информация о лингвокультурологических особенностях цветотонной лексики в английском и узбекском языках, месте лексикографии в узбекском и английском языках, активных лексических единицах в языках и в чем состоят их лексико-семантические особенности.

Ключевые слова: лексикон, лексикография, лексические единицы, фразеология, фразеологизмы, термины, словари.

Colors and dreams in our minds will definitely enrich our lives with the gray color of their plants. The colors excite us some equipment, and the dreams represent the creatures of sleep. The expression and identification of colors and dreams will be through our words. In English and Uzbek, words about colors and dreams are very common and have their own linguocultural characteristics.

First of all, words about color and dreams are distinguished in our languages by their original functions and significance. For example, in English, the word "color" represents color, but also the word "shade" represents dreams. And when it comes to Uzbek, the word "color" represents colors, and the word "dream" represents dreams. The specific meanings and forms of such words are formed from what is part of its linguocultural history and basic self-esteem.

In the second place, words about colors and dreams in Uzbek require attention inherent in this nationality. The intended use of colors and dreams in the tension of natural objects and resorts of Uzbekistan, in national clothing is an observer. And the fact that words are national and very correctly expressed in our language on independent topics indicates our sadness and love about this.

In this way, in Uzbek and English, words referring to the expression of colors and dreams were based on their linguistic peculiarities. These words actually help to explain the world of color and dreams for language learners, to express them.

In English and Uzbek, the linguistic and culturological characteristics of a color lexicon that expresses color:

Colors play an important role in language and culture, and each language may have unique characteristics in how colors are expressed and perceived. Here are some linguistic and culturological aspects of the color lexicon in English and Uzbek:

1. Basic Color Terms: Both English and Uzbek have basic color terms that categorize colors into primary and secondary categories. These terms are typically shared among speakers of the language and serve as the foundation for discussing colors.

2. Cultural Associations: Colors often carry cultural associations and symbolism. For example, in English, white is associated with purity or weddings, while in Uzbek culture, white is commonly associated with death and mourning. These cultural associations can vary and may be specific to certain contexts or traditions.

3. Color Idioms and Expressions: Both languages incorporate idiomatic expressions that involve colors. For instance, in English, someone might "feel blue" to express sadness, while in Uzbek, the expression "yashil qilmoq" (to turn green) can mean to become envious or jealous.

4. Color Perception and Naming: Studies have shown that different languages may perceive and categorize colors differently. For instance, English has distinct terms for "blue" and "green," while Uzbek traditionally uses the same term "ko'k" for both colors. This variation in color perception and naming can reflect cultural and linguistic differences.

5. Borrowing and Language Contact: Languages often borrow color terms from one another through language contact and cultural exchange. For example, the English language has borrowed color terms like "turquoise" from French, and Uzbek has borrowed terms like "sari" (yellow) from Turkish.

It's important to note that these characteristics are not exhaustive, and the color lexicon within any language can be a complex and multifaceted area of study.

As in the lexicon of a particular language, its terminological system distinguishes itself and the acquired layer. This is the case when terminological layers do not exist as separate systems in social consciousness, but their mutual variative, the fact that it is in synonymous, homonymic, plus, paronymic relations, together with this, the requirement of accuracy imposed on lexical, stylistic and phraseological terms, especially since the acquisition of the term is often different from the consumer lexicon shows that there are a number of problems, such as the presence of a subjective and individual character. This is in the formative, figurative, and grammatical properties of inclusions sometimes fakes are also the cause of occurrence, confusion, uncertainty and other negative situations. Therefore, serious research into these cases, it is of great importance to solve the problems that have arisen, to achieve terminological perfection. Lexical unit is-things, phenomena, their signs, etc. A word that can be expressed is a combination of words or another unit of language. The lexical unit is a semantic unit, a simple or complex concept in which words are expressed through a word or phrase, without changing the meaning of that unit, from none cannot be abandoned.

In English and Uzbek, interlaced words form a variety of constructed words: eyeglass, eye witness, eyeful, eyeless, to close ones eyes, up to ones eyes, in a pies eye, peep, peep, blink. It can be seen that the corresponding words in the two languages can have similar and different aspects according to the scope of meaning, valence and application.

It is known that lexical units and phraseological units are considered the linguistic unit that constitutes the vocabulary wealth of each language. They are in a state of readiness until speech as a unit of language. Also, in each language, lexical units have their own linguistic character. But in all languages, lexical and phraseological units serve as linguistic wealth. Polysemantic phraeological units serve to enrich the vocabulary of the language and speech, and embody the

meanings of emotional coloring. Therefore, we must be able to correctly apply lexical and phraseological terms in the time we translate. Only then will we achieve great success in lexicography and translation.

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